

The Influence of Green Knowledge, Environmental Concern and Wom on Intention to use Environmentally Friendly Straw Mediated by Green Attitude

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Abstract:- Lots of it rubbish plastic become problem environment that occurs At the moment. That matter increase intention use product friendly environment. Factor affecting intention use are green knowledge, environmental concern, word of mouth, and green attitude. The purpose of this research is to find out the influence of green knowledge, environmental concern, word of mouth, green attitude on intention use straw friendly environment. This research was conducted in Jabodetabek use questionnaire with 200 respondents through purposive sampling technique. Data analysis techniques using SmartPLS. Research result show that Green Attitude has an influence positive and significant on Intention to Use, Green Knowledge has an influence positive No significant on Intention to Use, Environmental concerns have an influence negative and not significant on Intention to Use, WOM has an influence positive significant towards Intention to Use, Green Attitude is positive and significant mediate connection between Green Knowledge and Intention to Use, positive Green Attitude or not significant No mediate connection Between Environmental Concern and Intention to Use and Green Attitude is positive and significant mediate connection between WOM and Intention to Use.

Keywords:- Green Knowledge, Environmental Concern, WOM, Green Attitude, Intention to Use.

I. INTRODUCTION

Issue Lots of it rubbish plastic become problem environment that occurs At the moment. If consumers No care with circumstances environment can result happen exploitation to environment and pollution environment the more Lots occurred (Riyanto et al., 2018). Damage an environment that doesn't dealt with with Good so will impact to man himself.

WWF (World Wide Fund for Nature) own campaign namely "No Plastic in Nature" which aims to improve broken system use approach holistic Where involve all aspect from cycle life start from government, perpetrator business and the public in operate this campaign. Since at that time, various holder interest other has make commitment public, start from prohibition straws and bags plastic until promise scale big like reduce, search source else, recycling repeat, and a lot again to reduce pollution rubbish plastic (Chaturvedi et al., 2020).

Fig. 1: Emergence waste in Indonesia in 2022

Arousal Indonesia has produced 19 million tons of waste from input carried out by 167 districts/cities throughout Indonesia in 2022. Results rubbish plastic is one of them originate from rubbish House resulting ladder from pattern life someone (Ambari, 2022). This is because per capita plastic consumption continues to increase, resulting in a plastic pollution problem (Chaturvedi et al., 2020).

With waste problems like this, the Government has stipulated Government Regulation Number 27 of 2020 concerning Waste Management Places with the 3R Principle (Reduce, Reuse, Recycle) or 3R TPS, namely places for collecting, sorting, using and recycling waste collected from household waste. With this regulation, the community is expected to be able to minimize the use of plastic and sort waste according to type (Lararenjana, 2020).

The main focus of the problem regarding plastic waste this time is to target the dangers of plastic straws, which are included as plastic waste that is difficult to handle, because plastic straw waste is difficult to sort and process due to its small size, but it is increasingly accumulating because it cannot be processed. so that it is left and ends up in the sea becoming microplastic which threatens biota and various marine products (Nathania, 2019). Through data revealed by econographics in June 2018, it was stated that Indonesia has the highest use of plastic straws in the world, reaching up to

93.2 million units per day (Djau, 2017). In response to this, many food outlets are starting to make movements to reduce plastic straws, or stop using plastic straws and replace them with environmentally friendly straws.

Apart from that, plastic waste is very difficult to decompose, it takes 500 to 1000 years to decompose. Plastic waste in the soil is very difficult and cannot be decomposed by microorganisms, which can cause the minerals in the soil, both organic and non-organic, to decrease over time, this causes the network of fauna in the soil such as worms and Other microorganisms in this area of soil find it difficult to find food and shelter. Apart from that, the oxygen levels in the soil are also decreasing, this can cause soil fauna to have difficulty breathing and die. Apart from the fauna in the soil, this also has an impact on the plants around the area (Budiyantoro, 2010).

Plastic straws contain polypropylene and Bisphenol A (BPA), which can leach harmful chemicals. Also, if it is exposed to heat, including from sunlight, plastic waste will become even more dangerous. Plastic straws are also made to last a long time, so they are not easily broken down and disrupt the marine ecosystem. One example is that in 2015 a turtle was found with a plastic straw stuck in its nose (Medika, 2019).

Fig. 2: Plastic straw stuck in turtle's nose

This image shows the struggle of Christine Figgner from Texas A&M University and her friends to remove a plastic straw from the nostrils of a male Olive Ridley sea turtle. The straw goes too deep into the nostril so pulling it out is not easy and must be done very carefully. Blood also slowly came out of the turtle's nose. After efforts that drained emotion and patience, Figgner and his friends succeeded in pulling out the plastic straw approximately 15 cm long. This sad experience is clear evidence of how dangerous plastic waste is for preserving the surrounding environment, especially used straws if they are thrown away or thrown into the sea. This plastic straw waste tends to be neglected because it is small and has no selling value for recycling (Yoenus, 2015).

The use of plastic straws in Indonesia can be said to be quite high. Data collected by Divers Clean Action shows that the use of plastic straws in Indonesia reaches 93,244,847 sticks every day, a length equivalent to 16,784 kilometers (Alamanda, 2022). This worrying environmental condition has given rise to sympathy from various groups, from the community to food providers, making this problem the current focus for improving the products they sell. This problem gives rise to people who care about the environment. Those who care are starting to take action to reduce waste which is one of the factors causing environmental damage and are starting to use environmentally friendly products (Kusuma et al., 2017).

The bad impact of using plastic straws for health can cause flatulence and contain dangerous chemicals.

Researchers conducted a pre-survey on 20 people who had never used environmentally friendly straws.

Table 1: Pre Results Survey Researcher

Variabel	Persentase
Green Knowledge	95%
Green Attitude	90%
Environmental Concern	85%
WOM	80%
Green Consumption	75%
Green Perceived Value	70%
Green Perceived Risk	65%
Green Trust	70%
Green Product	70%

After did it pre -survey of 20 respondents , shows results as diagram 1.1 shows that the most influential variable on consumer intention to use in use straw friendly environment are Green Knowledge, Environmental Concern, WOM and Green Attitude. To be more convincing this research , researcher has explained a number of results study previous related variables that will used.

Based on description background behind on as well as supported by the data obtained , researchers interested in doing study with title "The Influence of Green Knowledge, Environmental Concern and WOM Regarding Intention To Use Environmentally Friendly Straws Mediated by Green Attitude”.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Consumer behavior

Behavior consumer is A form displayed behavior consumer in make decision purchase product or services, with use source Power time, money and energy. Thinking including inside it related What will bought, why buy, when buy, where buy, how much? often buy, how much? often use, how evaluate pre and post purchase, evaluation on purchase next and how throw it away. (Schiffman et al., 2014).

Behavior consumer is about How individuals, groups and organizations do selection, purchase use and discard product, service, idea or experience to fulfill needs and desires them (Kotler, 2017).

B. Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is framework theoretical and methodological applied in a way broad to understand and predict behavior humans (Heiny et al., 2019). The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is development from the Theory of Action (TRA) which states that formation intention behavior somebody influenced by three factor that is: attitude, subjective norm, and control perceived behavior (perceived behavioral control) (Heiny et al., 2019). So that can concluded that formation intention behavior determined by motivation someone to use or buy something goods or service.

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) is explanatory theory all behavior Where somebody own ability to control self (LaMorte, 2022). This theory has always been become reference research that aims to test something attitudes and behavior public or someone (Ramadhani, 2011).

C. Social Cognitive Theory

Cognitive Theory Social (Social Cognitive Theory) was put forward by someone figure named Albert Bandura. Albert Bandura was born in 1925 in Canada. He accepts title doctorate on discourse knowledge psychology clinical from the University of Iowa, where pattern he thought influenced by the book "Social Learning and Imitation " by Miller and Dollard (1941). The new name "Social Cognitive Theory" was used in the 1970s and 1980s. The main idea of Bandura's thinking is also a development of Miller and Dollard's imitation learning thinking (Juhanis, 2021). In several publications, Bandura has described the social learning process which involves cognitive and behavioral factors that influence society in the social learning process. The rules show that behavior man is results from connection between three variables, namely Environmental Factors, Personal Factors, and Behavior.

SCT defines behavior man as something nature of interaction triadic, dynamic, and also reciprocal between factors personal, behavioral, and also factors environment (Wang, 2019). Internal interactions behavior a individual the form a cognitive process. Internal cognitive processes self a individual influenced by perception about efficacy self (self-efficacy) and also hope on results or outcome expectations (Wang, 2019). Efficacy self can interpreted as something individual beliefs about the capacity it has to complete something mission something work specific (Desivilya& Eizen, 2005).

D. Intention to use

Intention to use can interpreted as belief and will someone to shape attitude to object certain things and express them as more specific future behavior (Kwak, 2016). Intention (intention) is formed by each attitude to behavior (Purwanto et al., 2019). Intention to use is things to discuss about intention behavior someone, strength intention someone to do behavior certain conditions (Heiny et al., 2019).

Based on a number of the theory above, yes concluded that Intention to use is A form behavior desires and intentions somebody in use something product or service. As for indicators of Intention to Use is 1) Intention to use in Century front. 2) Intention to do it often use. 3) Intention to use in life daily. 4) Intention to use in a way regularly (De Leon, 2019).

E. Green Marketing

The concept of green marketing is not new thing. This concept was introduced by Bell and Emeri, as well as Feldman since 1971, who stated draft marketing has been misplaced, because only limited satisfying desire consumer but with ignore interest society and environment in period long (MC Daniel & Rylander, 1993).

Carry out green marketing concept in something company means enter consideration environment in all dimensions activity marketing carried out company (Crane, 2000). In existing literature, the concept of green marketing is variation terminology from environmental marketing, ecological marketing, green marketing, sustainable marketing, greener marketing (Prakash, 2002), and societal marketing (Kotler, 2003).

F. Green Attitude

Green attitude is predictor important for behavior , intention behave and constitute factor explainer from various type behavior individual (Teng & Wang, 2015). Usually Attitude as tool evaluation confidence someone to reflect dislikes and likes somebody to something object (Sudaryati et al., 2021). Attitude can direct behavior somebody Good to matter bad nor to matter OK , it depends

from results evaluation somebody to something behavior (Tran, 2019). Attitude is interaction in memory between object specific and summary evaluation (Maichum et al., 2016). Attitude is emotion psychological , which is directed through evaluation consumer . Something behavior tends to be more positive, if emotion psychological is also positive (Sari et al., 2019).

G. Word of Mouth

WOM is a most important process in communication to influence attitudes and behavior customers (Karimi Alavijeh et al., 2018). WOM delivers contribution to existence evaluation organizations, services, products spread across markets or social media (Chen et al., 2018). That matter important to determine behavior consumer when consider purchase product.

WOM is informal communication between people discussing information brands and companies in form goods or services (Amanah & Harahap, 2018). This is said as activity give information in marketing that shows somebody will tell others about experience Good in a way positive or negative when buy and consume product or service.

H. Environmental Concern

Environmental concerns are depicted as expression somebody in show his concern to issues environment (Teng et al., 2015). Indicators used _ in This research is : (1) Caring about situation on earth . Own role stuck situation on earth . 2) Humans must guard balance environment to remain life . Realize that guard balance environment is something necessity . 3) Humans often cause disturbances in nature which result in dangerous consequences. Know the consequences of natural disturbances caused by human activities. 4) Take action to reduce environmental damage. Engage in actions to reduce environmental damage (Onurlubaş, 2018).

I. Green Knowledge

Green Knowledge is information held _ somebody about interaction between humans and their environment (Lin & Niu, 2018). There are some thing that can be used to measure The role of Green Knowledge is: (1) Understanding. Understand draft product friendly environment and regulations applicable environment. (2) Knowledge to issue. Know issue or events that occur in the environment. (3) Knowledge regarding product use. Respondents know how to use environmentally friendly straws. (4) Expectations about green products for the environment. Environmentally friendly straws can meet environmental expectations (Agustini& Kusuma, 2016).

Based on these theories, the framework for this research is as follows:

Fig. 3: Framework Thinking

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research uses method quantitative with Partial Least Square Structural Equation Model (PLS SEM) approach. Statistical tools used for testing hypotheses This research is a Partial Least Square (Smart-PLS) program. Data will analyzed with two models. Measurement Model (Outer Model) is a connecting measurement model indicator with variable latent. Structural Model (Inner Model) is a structural model that connects between latent variable.

The variables used in This research is Green Knowledge (X1), Environmental Concern (X2), Word of Mouth (X3), Green Attitude (Y1), and Intention to Use (Y2). The data collection technique in this research is non - probability sampling using purposive sampling. Questionnaire with scale likertwill given to respondents who know about environmental issues and knowing about straw

friendly environment (eg straw bamboo, straw glass, food grade stainless steel straws, drinking straws food grade silicone).With the formula for calculating the sample size as follows:

$$\text{Indicator } x \text{ (numbers 5-10) } = \text{Number of samples } > 100 = 20 \times 7 = 140 \text{ samples respondents.}$$

IV. RESULTS

A. Evaluation of the Measurement Model (Outer Model)

This model defines How every indicator relate with variable its latency, or can said that the outer model can specify connection between latent variable with the indicators. The outer model is carried out by looking at the values of convergent validity, discriminant validity and construct reliability.

Fig. 4: Path DiagramOuter Loading

➤ *Test result Convergent Validity*

Testing *Convergent Validity* is the loading factor value on the latent variable with the indicators. This measurement is carried out to test validity of each variable. Data is said to be valid if obtain loading value > 0.7. Based on the path diagram, the measurement model in Figure 4 states that all over indicators for each variable own The outer loading / factor loading value is more than 0.7, which means all over

valid indicator. With thus, the research model has fulfil condition validity convergent which means that all over valid indicator in measure the construct.

Validity test converge also can done with look at AVE (*Average Variance Extracted*). It is declared that the construct meets convergent validity if the construct's AVE value is more than 0.5.

Table 2: Results of Factor Loading Values, Cronbach Alpha, CR, AVE

Variabel	Indikator	Outer Loading	AVE	α	CR	Ket
Nilai Green Knowledge	GK1	0,783	0,676	0,841	0,893	Lolos Uji
	GK2	0,777				Lolos Uji
	GK3	0,876				Lolos Uji
	GK4	0,847				Lolos Uji
Nilai Environmental Concern	EC1	0,819	0,660	0,739	0,852	Lolos Uji
	EC2	0,893				Lolos Uji
	EC4	0,716				Lolos Uji
Nilai WOM	WM1	0,761	0,693	0,891	0,918	Lolos Uji
	WM2	0,817				Lolos Uji
	WM3	0,845				Lolos Uji
	WM4	0,881				Lolos Uji
	WM5	0,852				Lolos Uji
Nilai Green Attitude	GA1	0,868	0,762	0,843	0,906	Lolos Uji
	GA2	0,91				Lolos Uji
	GA3	0,839				Lolos Uji
Intention to Use	IU1	0,872	0,775	0,903	0,932	Lolos Uji
	IU2	0,887				Lolos Uji
	IU3	0,912				Lolos Uji
	IU4	0,850				Lolos Uji

The table showing all over variable own AVE value more than 0.5, loading value > 0.7, Result show that all over variable study own composite reliability value is more than 0.7. so that can concluded all over variable has fulfil validity discriminant (Ghozali& Latan (2019:37).

Based on the resulting HTMT test results show that all between construct own HTMT value is less from 0.90. Thus, it can be stated that all constructs are valid in terms of discriminant validity.

➤ *Test result Discriminant Validity*

Validity test discriminant one of them did through the Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) test. Recommended HTMT value should be smaller of 0.85 (Clark & Watson 1995; Kline 2011) while others propose smaller value of 0.90 (Gold et al. 2001; Teo et al. 2008).

The discriminant validity test can also be carried out using the Fornell and Larcker method by comparing the square root of average variance extracted (AVE) value for each construct with the correlation between the construct and other constructs in the model. Validity test results distriminant based on the Fornell Lackers test obtained as follows:

Table 3: HTMT Test Results

Validity HTMT					
Variabel	EC	GA	GK	IU	WM
EC					
GA	0,596				
GK	0,502	0,524			
IU	0,482	0,789	0,431		
WM	0,736	0,623	0,363	0,557	

Table 4: Fornell and Larcker Test Results

Validity Fornell-Larcker					
Variabel	EC	GA	GK	IU	WM
EC	0,812				
GA	0,475	0,873			
GK	0,395	0,450	0,822		
IU	0,402	0,691	0,386	0,880	
WM	0,604	0,555	0,338	0,520	0,832

The result obtained every construct own greater value rather than correlation between construct One with other constructs in models. With so, then can stated that all construct has been valid validity discriminant.

B. Structural Model Evaluation (Inner Model)

Inner model testing can be done seen through mark coefficient determination of R-Square (R^2), effect size (F^2), and Q-Square predictive relevance (Q^2). While, level significance coefficient track used for testing hypothesis ie predict connection between latent variable.

➤ **R-Square Value Test Results (R^2)**

Coefficient determination R Square (R^2) shows how much big variable exogenous explain variable its endogenous.

Table 6: R Square Value (R^2)

Variabel	R Square
Intention to Use (Y)	0,509
Green Attitude (Z)	0,397

Table 7: Effect Size Value (F^2)

Hubungan	f^2	Effect Size
Environmental Concern → Intention to Use	0,000	Tidak ada
Environmental Concern → Green Attitude	0,020	Kecil
Green Attitude → Intention to Use	0,378	Besar
Green Knowledge → Intention to Use	0,008	Kecil
Green Knowledge → Green Attitude	0,097	Sedang
WOM → Intention to Use	0,040	Kecil
WOM → Green Attitude	0,149	Sedang

Based on table category above, the value of f^2 in the relationship between Environmental Concern and Intention to Use is 0.000, which means No has an effect size, the f^2 value on the relationship between Environmental Concern and Green Attitude is 0.020, which means has a small effect size, relationship between Green Attitude and Intention to Use, the f^2 value is 0.378, which means has a large effect size, relationship between Green Knowledge and Intention to Use, the f^2 value is 0.008, which means has a small effect size, relationship between Green Knowledge and Green Attitude, the f^2 value is 0.097, which means has a medium effect size, meanwhile connection between WOM and Intention to Use the f^2 value is 0.040, which means has a small effect size, apart from that, the relationship between WOM and Green Attitude, the f^2 value is 0.149, which means has a medium effect size.

Based on The R-Square value in Table 6 shows that The R-Square value of the Intention to Use (Y) variable is 0.509. This value means that variability The Intention to Use construct can be explained by variability the Green Attitude construct was 50.9%. This value indicates category “medium” relationship, meanwhile the rest 49.1 % is explained by other variables outside those studied. Meanwhile, the R-Square value of the Green Attitude (Z) variable is of 0.397. The R-Square value shows influence Simultaneous Green Knowledge, Environmental Concern and WOM on Green Attitude is 39.7% indicating category “Medium” relationship, meanwhile the rest 60.3 % is explained by other variables outside those studied.

➤ **Effect Size Test Results**

Effect size or F^2 use to know how much large exogenous latent variable can supports endogenous latent variables.

➤ **Test result Predictive Relevance (Q^2)**

The Q^2 value of the model is more than 0, indicating that the model has good predictive relevance, whereas Q^2 value is less from 0 indicates the model is lacking has predictive relevance.

Table 8: Predictive Relevance Value (Q^2)

Variabel	SSO	SSE	Q^2
GA	525	375,192	0,285
IU	700	435,871	0,377

Based on Test Results Commuality Cross Validation of Constructs in table 8 above can seen that all variable own greater value from 0. With thereby so can interpreted that all variable own very strong value, where number highest that

is with Q2 value = 0.377 meaning that the Intention to Use variable has mark strong and relevant predictions.

➤ *Testing Hypothesis*

Testing hypothesis PLS-SEM analysis in this study used significance 5% or with tolerance error $\alpha = 0.05$. As for

taking decision in PLS-SEM analysis for hypotheses with a 5% significance test is If $|t\text{-statistic}|$ value > 1.96 or mark significance ($p\text{-value}$) < 0.05 and the path coefficient value is positive.

Fig. 5: Path Diagram Path Coefficient & T-Statistics Structural Model (Inner Model)

Based on this model then on testing Direct and indirect hypotheses are accepted are H1, H3, H4, H7, H8 and H10.

Whereas rejected hypothesis _ are H2, H5, H6, and H9. The following results are presented in table form :

Table 9: Test Results Direct Hypothesis

HIPOTESIS		Path Coefficients (β)	Standard Deviation (STDEV)	T Statistics (O/STDEV)	P-Values	Keterangan	Hasil	Mediasi
H ₁	GK → GA	0,266	0,106	2,520	0,012	Diterima	Positif Signifikan	-
H ₂	EC → GA	0,141	0,093	1,521	0,128	Ditolak	Positif Tidak Signifikan	-
H ₃	WM → GA	0,379	0,088	4,308	0,000	Diterima	Positif Signifikan	-
H ₄	GA → IU	0,555	0,087	6,353	0,000	Diterima	Positif Signifikan	-
H ₅	GK → IU	0,074	0,083	0,898	0,369	Ditolak	Positif Tidak Signifikan	-
H ₆	EC → IU	-0,007	0,070	0,096	0,923	Ditolak	Negatif Tidak Signifikan	-
H ₇	WM → IU	0,191	0,073	2,626	0,009	Diterima	Positif Signifikan	-
H ₈	GK → GA → IU	0,148	0,052	2,824	0,005	Diterima	Positif Signifikan	Mediasi Full
H ₉	EC → GA → IU	0,078	0,055	1,418	0,156	Ditolak	Positif Tidak Signifikan	Non Mediasi
H ₁₀	WM → GA → IU	0,211	0,063	3,356	0,001	Diterima	Positif Signifikan	Mediasi Parsial

V. DISCUSSION

A. *H1: The influence of Green Knowledge has a positive and significant effect on Green Attitude*

H1 in this study was accepted. These results are in accordance with research in line with research by Riyanto & Suhanti (2021) where Green Knowledge influences Green Attitude.

This shows that respondents in this study considered that himself is a friendly person environment . The level of information possessed by the respondent about something problem environment will be very decisive his opinion about problem that , increasingly high level of Green Knowledge possessed respondent , then the more high level of awareness and attitude to environment the . Therefore , someone who has Green Knowledge will own intention to use straw friendly environment.

B. H2: Influence of Environmental Concern on Green Attitude

H2 in this study was rejected. These results are in agreement with study Anggraini et al, (2023), where *Environmental Concern* No influential positive and not significant to *Green Attitude*. The analysis results obtained in this research are why obtained no result significant, because If seen from Environmental Concern's descriptive test results had the highest influence is "I have concern to nature". so that seen that opinion respondents about straw friendly environment get The response was positive, however it turns out matter the No significant whether the response is positive the capable make respondents other own good attitude to straw friendly environment, so This is something that needs to be evaluated by business people in the future to do more approach to consumer in choose friendly product environment.

C. H3: Influence of WOM on Green Attitude

H3 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with research by Mehrad & Mohammadi (2017), where there is Influence Positive and Significant between WOM and *Green Attitude*, and this is something that business people really pay attention to in order to gain experience consumer in use product the can promoted to others and finally give positive attitude for consumer other.

D. H4: Influence Green Attitude To Intention to Use

H4 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with study Ryantari & Giantari (2020), where there is Influence Positive and Significant between *Green Attitude* with *Intention to Use*. This shows that in this research Green Attitude of respondents in respond importance friendly the environment is very good, which means respondents in This research is dominated by respondents who have attitude care will environment. Green Attitude from positive environment is point a good start to motivate intention respondents to use safe product to environment.

E. H5: Influence Green Knowledge To Intention to Use

H5 in this study was rejected. These results are in agreement with study Wahyuningtias, L. & Artanti, Y. (2020), where Nothere is Influence *Green Knowledge* to *Intention to Use*. Green Knowledge indeed should will influential positive on Intention to Use straws friendly environment. Price of straws friendly more expensive environment in comparison straw plastic ordinary and lacking education to possible environment creating Green Knowledge is not influential significant on Intention to Use straws friendly environment. Respondents who have knowledge and awareness tall to environment will choose friendly products environment although price a little more expensive.

F. H6: Influence Environmental Concern To Intention to Use

H6 in this study was rejected. These results are consistent with study Siagian, D. et al (2021) where *Environmental concerns* No proven own influence significant to *Green Purchase Intention* and not in line with

study Anggraini et al (2023) where *environmental concerns* have an influence positive significant on *home Purchase Intention friendly environment*. This shows that in this study the respondents own weak Environmental Concern score to straw friendly environment. Through descriptive tests least influence from Environmental Concern is "I started do activities reduce damage environment" means respondents No own high level of concern to begin with do activity reduce damage environment with use straw friendly environment.

G. H7: Influence Word of Mouth To Intention to Use

H7 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with research by Wibowo & Wulandari (2022) where There is significant influence from *word of mouth* to decision purchase. This shows that the more good product review so the more Many people also decide to buy product.

H. H8: Green Attitude Mediate The Relationship Between Green Knowledge and Intention to Use

H8 in this study was accepted. These results are in agreement with study Anggraini et al (2023) where Effect mediation from Attitude role positive and significant between connection *Green Knowledge* to *Purchase Intention*.

If seen from hypothesis test results The relationship between Green Knowledge and Green Attitude has positive and significant relationship whereas connection between Green Knowledge and Intention to Use have positive relationship However No significant. This can said that someone who considers himself a friendly person environment Not yet Of course have a good Green Attitude to straw friendly environment, therefore someone who considers himself a friendly person environment Not yet Of course have the Intention to Use to use straw friendly environment. Someone who considers himself has a friendly Green Attitude environment can turn away from products that don't friendly environment, this is caused by several factor. For example like something the situations and conditions that create it urge Because must do it.

I. H9: Green Attitude Mediate The Relationship Between Environmental Concern and Intention to Use

H9 in this study was rejected. These results are in agreement with study Anggraini et al (2023) where Effect mediation from Attitude role positive and not significant between Environmental Concern's relationship to Purchase Intention. This can said that someone who is Environmentally Concerned has a positive Green Attitude in wish to use straw friendly environment, however desire the No significant whether someone the want to use friendly straw environment only Because want to follow trend, right Because awareness will environment. This is shown in the descriptive test at Environmental Concern which says that "I started do activities reduce damage environment." so that can concluded that Someone who is Environmentally Concerned has a positive Green Attitude to straw friendly environment However attitude the No persist.

J. H10: Green Attitude Mediate The Relationship Between Word Of Mouth and Intention to Use

H10 in this study is accepted. These results are in agreement with study Tabbane& Hamouda (2013) where Effect mediation from *Attitude* role positive and significant between connection *Word of Mouth* to *Purchase Intention*. As results decision hypothesis H10 states that WOM has an influence significant to decision purchase, then effect variable trust in mediate connection between WOM and decisions purchase is as partial mediation. This is because Good through or without through variable *Green Attitude* , the WOM variable directly influences significant to decision purchase .

VI. CONCLUSION

A. Conclusion

Conclusions of This research is:

- Green Knowledge is influential positive and significant towards Green Attitude
- Environmental Concern has an influence positive and not significant towards Green Attitude
- Word of Mouth matters positive and significant towards Green Attitude
- Green Attitude has an effect positive and significant towards Intention to Use
- Green Knowledge is influential positive and not significant towards Intention to Use
- Environmental Concern has an influence negative and not significant towards Intention to Use
- Word of Mouth matters positive and significant towards Intention to Use
- Effect Green Attitude mediation has an effect positive and significant on Green Knowledge on Intention to Use in use straw friendly environment
- Effect Green Attitude mediation has an effect positive and not significant on Environmental Concern on Intention to Use in use straw friendly environment
- Effect Green Attitude mediation has an effect positive and significant in Word of Mouth on Intention to Use in use straw friendly environment.

B. Suggestion

➤ Theoretical

Researcher propose suggestions to researcher Next, who is interested with discussion about Intention to Use and Green Attitude with the theme "green behavior". If seen from results study R-Square value obtained is 39.7% for the mediating variable and 50.9% for the dependent variable. So that Still there is a number of percent that influences Green Attitude and Intention to Use.

➤ Practical

Based on research that has been carried out and is based on acceptable results, then researcher recommend to consumers who will _ do use straw friendly environment with notice a number of matter related to Intention to Use , namely Green Knowledge, Environmental Concern, Word of Mouth, and Green Attitude.

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